

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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COORDINATION OF THE ACTIVITIES OF CREATIVE TEAMS

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Abstract: In this article, activities in the field of culture and industry ideas about the peculiarities of growing creative teams is maintained. Creative teams have a number of features. The most important of them is that the processes taking place within the team are characterized by the struggle of two trends. One Direction is to achieve the team's Jeeps as a particular social group that requires conformism from its members, while the other is a required creation for an entirely free individual who, by its nature, stands in contrast to conformism.

Key words: coordination, task, conditions, organization, culture, art, institution, management, strategy, value, citizenship, modern, spirituality, ideology, task, government, field, direction, activity, law, system.

КООРДИНАЦИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ КОЛЛЕКТИВОВ

Аннотация: В данной статье сохраняется деятельность в сфере культуры и промышленности, представления об особенностях формирования творческих коллективов. Творческие коллективы обладают рядом особенностей. Самая главная из них заключается в том, что процессы, происходящие внутри коллектива, характеризуются борьбой двух тенденций. Одно направление — достижение джипов коллектива как особой социальной группы, требующей от своих членов конформизма, а другое — обязательное создание совершенно свободного индивида, который по своей природе противостоит конформизму.

Ключевые слова: координация, задача, условия, организация, культура, искусство, учреждение, управление, стратегия, ценность, гражданство, современный, духовность, идеология, задача, правительство, сфера, направление, деятельность, закон, система.

Coordination is one of the important tasks of management, the implementation of which consists in coordinating the internal state of the organization with its external conditions, ensuring compliance in the work of all

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branches of the system and the establishment of rational relations between them and mutual cooperation between the systems. Also, coordination is the task between the elements of the control system, which is aimed at ensuring mutual communication and coordination by establishing rational connections (communications) between them. The character of these connections can be diverse, since it depends on the processes being coordinated. Therefore, when performing these tasks, it is possible to use a variety of documentary sources (reports, information, analytical information) and the results that arise when discussing problems at meetings, councils, when interviewing. A large role in this is played by technical means of communication, which help to quickly focus on deviations from the normal course of the organization's work. In the conditions of the growth of independence and responsibility of leaders and performers at all stages, an increase in the so-called informal ties occurs, which ensure the horizontal coordination of work performed at one stage of the management structure. At the same time, the need for vertical coordination is reduced, in which the control structure remains "flat". In the field of culture and art, the coordination method is widely used in the implementation of management processes, as in manufacturing, economics and other fields. This situation is more reflected in the leadership of the activities of creative communities and associations under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Culture. Before talking about the Coordination of the activities of creative teams, it is appropriate to dwell on the concepts of "creativity" and "team".

The National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan defines the term creativity as follows:

Creativity is the activity of a person to create new material and spiritual blessings. In it, human thinking, memory, imagination, attention, will are actively involved, all knowledge, experience, talent are manifested. Creativity is initially born in the human imagination. It will be a real, complete creation if it is recognized by society. Creativity enriches and develops culture. Unsharply can be divided into two: scientific and artistic creation.

A team is an organized group of two or more people on the path of a specific goal. Relying on the above, the concept of a creative team can be described as follows: a creative team is a creative team that aims to provide cultural service to the interests of society and humanity in its main activities, is oriented in different directions and genres of culture and art, is engaged in cultural service with the same goals and ideas. For example, creative teams are the Yalla ensemble, Surkhan group,

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Maqamists ensemble, as well as 37 professional theaters and some dance groups operating in our country. The country provides conditions and opportunities for the development of traditional and academic music and dance art, professional skills of performers and identification of talented young people, and provides comprehensive support and stimulation of the creativity of music performers and dance teams. At the same time, the complex solution of the tasks of the state policy to support the development of music and dance art necessitates the need to improve the management system in this area. There is also a need to further strengthen the material and technical base of artistic communities and orchestras, to solve the issues of creating a system of the necessary level of popularization of art.

The role of cultural centers operating in our republic is significant in the further development of the activities of these professional teams and the organization of cooperation with amateur teams. The collaborative activities of each team will not have any impact on the future creative process of both professional and amateur teams. It is appropriate to ask the question, What kind of benefit does the activity of cooperation with professional teams bring for the Cultural Center, Firstly, if the Professional creative team shows musical numbers in its repertoire in remote areas, it serves as a master class for amateur teams; when the Cultural Center organizes its collaborative activities, its free time is organized meaningfully for the residents of the; at the initiative of the Cultural Center, the organization of concert programs of these communities has a positive effect on the existing cash income in the annual load of the Cultural Center; the orientation of the child by the population towards culture and art after organized cultural events or concerts, sets the stage for an increase in the number of paid circles in cultural centers. An example of one of the processes in practice is that the dance ensemble “the beauties of Bukhara” under the Bukhara Philharmonic established amateur teams under the Bukhara city cultural centers have established extensive cooperation. Participants who have perfectly absorbed the art of dance in their joint performances and amateur circles at cultural events will be able to join this troupe and participate in events at the regional level. It is worth mentioning that the creative teams in turn are two: 1. Professional creative teams are formed-mainly under the Philharmonic and its territorial divisions. For each of the employees operating in these communities, a monthly salary is paid based on the schedule of the states.

2. Amateur communities-mainly organized under cultural centers, the state is allocated by the regional financial authorities depending on the activities of the team

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only if these communities have the title of people. Amateurism and its one-of-a-kind folklore ethnographic communities are now a phenomenal phenomenon characteristic of the culture of many peoples of the world. Many researchers who have studied this phenomenon evaluate folklore and amateur communities as one thing, that is, the activity of communities as a manifestation, component of folklore. Due to independence, the activities of amateur communities now continue in cultural centers. This makes it easier for these amateur communities to take advantage of the opportunities created by the state.

Most of the mass events are now also gaining popularity in a variety of ways, with forms of execution using techniques. The appearance of amateur teams in public performances is important in the ideological-spiritual education of the participants of the event. The role of amateur teams is also considered great in the formation of an artistic performance. Artistic performance is important in the development of human thought, especially in the spiritual education of young people.

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